

3- Evaluation for Participants

After analyzing the illustrative scenario and the generated artifacts, please answer the following questions.

Use the following scale for the quantitative questions:

- 1 – Strongly disagree**
- 2 – Disagree**
- 3 – Neither**
- 4 – Agree**
- 5 – Strongly agree**

Construct 1: Job Relevance

Assesses the extent to which OpenUP4Exp is perceived as applicable to the evaluator's professional context, particularly in activities related to explainability in Intelligent Systems.

1. OpenUP4Exp appears relevant to activities related to explainability.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**

 2. The activities presented in the scenario seem applicable to my work context.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**

 3. The artifacts produced in the scenario are useful to support the understanding of explainability
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**
-

Construct 2: Output Quality

Assesses the perception of the quality, consistency, and level of professionalism of the artifacts generated by the framework.

4. The artifacts presented (generated by each activity/worker) exhibit good quality.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**

 5. The process described in the scenario suggests the production of consistent results.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**

 6. The sequence of activities indicates that the framework can generate structured and appropriate artifacts.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**
-

Construct 3: Result Demonstrability

Assesses whether the outputs produced by the framework are comprehensible, observable, and communicable.

7. I can clearly perceive the benefits of OpenUP4Exp.
 - Strongly disagree**
 - Disagree**
 - Neither**
 - Agree**
 - Strongly agree**

8. The results of the framework are easy to communicate to other professionals.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither

Agree

Strongly agree

9. The results presented in the scenario are tangible and understandable.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither

Agree

Strongly agree

Construct 4: Anticipated Enjoyment

Refers to the expectation of a positive experience when using the framework, considering intrinsic motivation and initial acceptance.

10. I would consider the use of OpenUP4Exp a positive experience in my work context.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither

Agree

Strongly agree

General Feedback

Q1 – Are there any additional recommendations, perceived gaps, or points for improvement that you consider important for the evolution of OpenUP4Exp?